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Khasanxonova Durdonakhon Juraxon kizi
(Students of SamSIFL)

Annotation. *The article describes the main stages of the translation process and what categories the translator uses when comparing units of the source language and the target language. An attempt is made to distinguish between such concepts as a translation strategy, a method of translation, a translation technique or a translation transformation. The main classifications of translation transformations currently described in the linguistic literature are also presented.*

Key words: *rendering, interpreting, translation, approaches, translation mechanism, translation strategy, translation transformation, translation method, language.*

Despite the relatively young age of translation theory or translation studies as a science, there are currently many works devoted to the theory of translation. This is not surprising, since all famous translators have their own points of view on the vision of the translation process and its basic principles.

The direct switching method is based on a sequence of formal negotiation rules; is more advanced and is based on a series of consistent rules that make it possible to equalize the syntactic and semantic structures in the respective languages. Some experts believe that correspondences can be established most efficiently and economically using some kind of universal intermediary language (either a natural language, or perhaps even an artificial one). Despite the advantages of this type of translation, many scholars believe that such approaches to translation are of more theoretical interest and are not of particular practical value.

The main concept of the theory of translation is, of course, the very concept of “translation”. Many scholars and translators define this concept, although sometimes from different, sometimes completely opposite positions. L. S. Barkhudarov, one of the founders of the Russian theory of translation, gives the following definition: “Translation is the process of converting a speech work in one language into a speech work in another language while maintaining an unchanged content plan, i.e. meaning” [2].

After all the transformations carried out, the translator at the third stage of the translation process needs to think about the equivalence of the translation and its adequacy, however, many researchers share these two concepts. The concept of equivalence is one of the fundamental ones in the theory of translation, since the achievement of equivalence, equivalence of the texts of the original and the translation is the main task of the translator. Most researchers believe that the absolute equivalence of the text of the original and the translation is impossible due to semantic, structural and pragmatic differences between the source text and the translated text, and recognize the relativity of the truly achievable equivalence of the translation. The interpretation and specification of the concept of equivalence differ.

According to O. A. Akhmanova, translation is “the transfer of the semantic content and stylistic features of an utterance in one language by means of another language” [1]. In the view of I.R. Galperin, “translation is the transfer of the semantic content and stylistic features of an utterance in one language by means of another language” [3]. The definition of A. V. Fedorov also attracts attention: “To translate means to express correctly and completely by means of one language what has already been expressed earlier by means of another language” [4].

In all the above definitions, translation is interpreted as a kind of activity carried out by a translator. Consequently, most of the authors define translation as a process, as a result of which a text appears in another language. Speaking of translation as a process, linguists distinguish two phases in it:

- a) the comprehension phase, during which the translator analyzes the source text, taking into account its semantic, grammatical, stylistic and other features;
- b) the phase of the actual translation, which is the reproduction of the content of the source text by means of another language.

If the first phase consists in the first acquaintance of the translator with the publication that he intends to translate, then the second phase involves the implementation of all that constitutes translation competence, as well as the achievement through this implementation of the final result - the creation of a translated text. What is the requirement for translation as a final result? This requirement is as follows: the translated text must accurately and holistically convey the content of the original, while maintaining its stylistic features. While the criterion of accuracy implies the identity of information, the criterion of integrity means the transfer of information by equivalent means of the target language.

In other words, the translation must convey not only what is expressed by the original, but also as it is expressed in it.

When translating, the translator first of all determines the method of translation, i.e. the measure of informational order for the translated text. The first step in choosing a method of ordering is to determine in what form the source text should be presented in the translating culture: in whole or in part. Depending on the communicative task, either a full or an abbreviated translation is selected at this stage (in some sources it is also called abstract, although these terms are not quite adequate).

All types of texts can belong to an abridged translation: from a simple business letter to a novel. The result of using abbreviated translation is such texts as theses, summaries, abstracts, annotations, digests, etc. In essence, abbreviated translation is performed by one of the fundamental methods of translation: selective or functional translation.

Selective translation as a method of abbreviated translation consists in the selection of key units of the source text, from the point of view of the translator, and their full translation. All other components of the source text with this method are discarded as secondary in terms of achieving the result and are not subject to translation at all. This method is quite often used to retell business topics, newspaper materials, scientific articles and messages, reports, etc. in a thesis-abstract form.

Functional translation as a way of abbreviated transmission of the source text in another language consists in arranging the translated text from functionally transformed units of the

source text. A typical example of such a method of translation is the so-called paraphrase, when a whole large work is paraphrased in a simplified version.

In contrast to the abbreviated full translation is aimed at a thorough reproduction of all components of the information orderliness of the source text in terms of the target language. Full translation can be carried out in various ways, but the following can be considered the most common: literal or word-for-word translation, semantic and communicative translations.

Literal translation consists in the word-for-word reproduction of the text in the units of the target language, if possible, even preserving the order of the elements in essence; literal translation is relatively rarely used for communicative purposes and usually has an exclusively scientific scope. Thus, for the purposes of linguistic analysis, literal translation is considered to be preferable to other ways of presenting the source text, since it allows conveying information about the very syntactic structure of the original.

Semantic translation consists in the possibility of a more complete transfer of the contextual meaning of the elements of the source text in terms of the target language. The process of semantic translation is a natural interaction of two strategies: the strategy of focusing on the mode of expression adopted in the target language, and the strategy of focusing on preserving the features of the original form of expression. The first strategy is applied to commonly used lexical and grammatical elements of the source text, such as standard syntactic structures, sentence length, typical metaphors, morphological structures, widespread general cultural and popular science terms and expressions, etc. The second strategy is appropriate when translating non-standard, author's turns, original stylistic devices, unusual vocabulary, etc.

Semantic translation, as a rule, is applied to texts that have a high socio-cultural status: important historical documents, works of high literature, unique epic samples, etc. It is also required when transferring texts such as technical instructions, most scientific publications, and, of course, legal documents.

The communicative method consists in choosing such a way of transmitting the initial information, which leads to a translated text with an adequate initial impact on the recipient. The main object in this method of translation is not only the linguistic composition of the source text, but also its meaningful and emotional-aesthetic meaning. Moreover, unlike functional translation, communicative translation does not allow any reductions or simplifications of the source material. In essence, what in everyday life is often called literary and, in particular, literary translation, in fact, is precisely a communicative translation that takes into account - or programming - the pragmatics of the recipient. This method is optimal for most fiction, journalism, part of scientific, theoretical and popular science texts, etc.

When choosing one or another method of translation, the translator, in addition to all other circumstances, is also guided by the considerations that in its pure form, any of the methods in the real translation process rarely works: as a rule, most complex texts are translated using various methods, but one of them is the leading one and determines the nature of the relationship between the source and the translated text as a whole, dictating both the conditions for dividing the source text, and the definition of translation units, as well as the choice of translation techniques by which the source text is directly converted into the target text.

Having considered the process of translation, we can compare it with the movement of thought, and this movement takes place in the direction from the general to the particular: from understanding the specifics of translation - to understanding the purpose of the translation - further to the formation of a translation strategy that corresponds to the goal - and, as a result, to choice of translation methods or translation transformations.

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